

Daily work life during the Philby-Ryckmans-Lippens mission and 2023 expedition: new methodologies in a traditional settings.

While the Philby-Ryckmans-Lippens conducted the expedition with a Jeep and Studebaker truck, the 2023 expedition team was driven in 12 4-wheel drives.

Picknicks with traditional Saudi dishes at the cultural heritage sites of Ukhdūd (1951-52) and Jebel Māsīl (2003)

The Ryckmans teams 1951-2023 were assisted by local guides, leading the researchers to the petroglyph sites.

The two Ryckmans teams 1951-2023 working at the Jebel Māsīl. Jacques Ryckmans manually copies the inscription (Ry 510) from the ladder, while the 2023 team focuses on digital photography.

Het dagelijkse veldwerk tijdens de Philby-Ryckmans-Lippens missie en de 2023 expeditie: nieuwe methodologieën binnen een traditioneel kader.

Vie professionnelle sur le terrain lors de la mission Philby-Ryckmans-Lippens et de l'expédition 2023 : nouvelles méthodologies dans un cadre traditionnel.